

A minimal classical model illustrating superdeterminism and the violation of Bell inequalities

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Abstract

We present an extremely simple linear dynamical model which, through initial conditions modified as a function of the measurement settings, produces violations of the Clauser-Horne-Shimony-Holt (CHSH) inequality. The model is not a classical counterexample to Bell's theorem, since it explicitly breaks the assumption of independence between hidden variables and measurement settings. Instead, it provides a clear example of *superdeterminism* and can be used as an educational tool to illustrate the crucial role of the assumptions of locality, realism, and freedom of choice in Bell's theorem.

1 Introduction

Bell's theorem and the associated inequalities are derived under three main assumptions: realism, locality, and measurement independence. Experimentally observed violations confirm that at least one of these assumptions must be abandoned in the physical world.

Superdeterminism constitutes one of the possible loopholes: in this scenario, measurement choices are not independent but correlated with hidden variables. Although often considered implausible, this possibility is logically consistent. Here we present a minimal *toy model* that violates CHSH by abandoning measurement independence.

2 The model

We consider a linear dynamical system with state $X = (x_1, x_2)^T$ evolving as a harmonic oscillator:

$$\dot{X} = AX, \quad A = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ -1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}.$$

The output is the projection along an angle θ :

$$y(\theta, t) = [\cos \theta \quad \sin \theta] X(t),$$

with dichotomic measurement

$$m(\theta) = \text{sign}[y(\theta, t_1)] \in \{-1, +1\}.$$

Initial conditions depend on Alice's and Bob's settings:

$$x_1(0) = r_1 + \lambda \cos(\vartheta_A), \quad x_2(0) = r_2 + \lambda \cos(\vartheta_B),$$

with r_1, r_2 Gaussian noise. This dependence breaks measurement independence \Rightarrow superdeterminism.

3 Numerical results

Simulations varying λ show:

- $\lambda = 0$: $S \approx 2$, with $\sim 50\%$ spurious violations due to noise;
- $\lambda \approx 2$: maximum $S \approx 2.62$, close to the quantum limit $2\sqrt{2}$;
- large λ : deterministic again, $S = 2$.

Figure 1: S mean values as a function of λ .

4 Educational discussion

The model reproduces quantum-like statistics, but only because measurement independence is broken. Its pedagogical value is that it clearly shows:

- Bell inequalities rely on specific assumptions;
- dropping independence yields violations trivially;
- this helps students discuss locality, realism, and freedom of choice.

5 Conclusions

This simple model is not a counterexample to Bell's theorem, but a transparent demonstration of superdeterminism. It is valuable as an educational tool in teaching the foundations of quantum mechanics.

References

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